

RESEARCH PAPER

Effect of Hydrocooling and Storage Condition on Postharvest Quality of Coriander Leaf

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ABSTRACT

An experiment was conducted to evaluate the influence of different hydrocooling (HC) treatments and storage (S) conditions on the postharvest quality of coriander leaves. The two-factor experiment employed a completely randomized design (CRD) with five replications. Four hydrocooling treatments (cool water at 5 ± 0.5 °C) were designated as factor A: T₁ for 5 minutes (min) HC, T₂ for 10 min HC, T₃ for 20 min HC, and T₄ for 40 min HC. Additionally, two low-temperature storage conditions (at 4 ± 0.5 °C) were considered as factor B: S₁ for chiller storage and S₂ for refrigerator storage. Significant variations were observed concerning different hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions. The 10-minute hydrocooling treatment (T₂) demonstrated an extended shelf life of 8.67 days. However, T₁ showed the highest pH (6.38), ascorbic acid content (5.0%), and anthocyanin content (0.33 µg/g), while T₄ exhibited the highest titratable acidity (0.23%). On the other hand, storage condition S₂ (refrigerator storage) resulted in the longest shelf life (8.17 days), highest pH (6.45), titratable acidity (0.21%), ascorbic acid content (3.75%), and anthocyanin content (0.28 µg/g). The combined effects of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions exerted significant influences on most studied parameters for up to 10 days of storage. The optimum combination, observed in T₂S₂, resulted in the maximum shelf life (9.33 days), the highest pH (6.50) at 10 days after storage, and the maximum anthocyanin content (0.26 µg/g) at the same point. Conversely, the highest titratable acidity (0.26%) and ascorbic acid content (5.01%) at 10 days after storage were found in T₄S₂ and T₁S₂, respectively. Consequently, it can be inferred that the optimal condition for enhancing most postharvest qualities of coriander leaves involves a 10-minute hydrocooling treatment (T₂), storage condition S₂ (refrigerator storage), and the sample treated with 10 minutes of hydrocooling and stored in the refrigerator (T₂S₂).

Key words: Coriander leaves, Hydrocooling, Postharvest quality, Shelf life, Storage condition

Introduction

Coriander, scientifically identified as *Coriandrum sativum* L., is an herbaceous plant with an annual life cycle and is categorized within the Apiaceae family. Widely recognized as "Dhonia" in Bangladesh, this plant holds a prominent place in Ayurvedic medicine. All parts of the coriander plant are utilized as a flavoring agent and traditional remedies for various disorders in folk medicine across different civilizations (Sahib *et al.*, 2012). The plant is entirely edible, with fresh leaves commonly used for garnishing and found in numerous dishes such as chutneys and salads. The seeds exhibit an almost oval and spherical shape, providing a gentle, sweet, slightly tangy citrus taste accompanied by a touch of sage. In Bangladesh, the annual production of

coriander seeds in the 2020-21 fiscal year (FY) reached approximately 21,518.84 metric tons, while the leaf production was about 6,209.00 metric tons (BBS 2021). This highly aromatic plant has played a crucial role in maintaining human health and enhancing the quality of life for thousands of years (Dhankaret *et al.*, 2011). The leaves of coriander are abundant in vitamins, minerals, and iron. They contain high amounts of vitamin C (up to 160 mg/100 g), vitamin A (up to 12 mg/100 g), thiamine, zinc, and dietary fiber (Girenko, 1982). Additionally, the plant is abundant in essential oils crucial for growth and proper brain function (Nadeemet *et al.*, 2013). Furthermore, coriander is utilized in the treatment of various disorders, including digestive tract disorders, respiratory tract

Paul et al. disorders, and urinary tract infections. Studies have highlighted its pharmacological activities, such as antioxidant (Darughe *et al.*, 2012), anti-diabetic (Eidi *et al.*, 2012), anti-mutagenic (Cortes *et al.*, 2004), anti-lipidemic (Sunil *et al.*, 2012), and anti-spasmodic (Alison and Peter, 1999) properties.

Transpiration, leading to water loss from leaves, results in qualitative and quantitative losses of vegetables (Finger and Vieira, 1997). Leafy vegetables like coriander are prone to water loss and wilting post-harvest, affecting color, appearance, metabolism, and nutritional quality. Given their perishable nature, various postharvest methods, including forced air, cold water, ice, and vacuum cooling, can be employed to enhance food conservation, prolonging longevity and quality (Teruel, 2008). Among these methods, rapid cooling is cost-effective and efficient, and hydrocooling, utilizing ice or cold water, stands out as a simple and practical conservation technique. This method expeditiously removes field heat from freshly harvested products, slowing metabolism and reducing product deterioration (Franca, 2015). Furthermore, the optimal preservation of fresh culinary herbs is achieved through low-temperature and high-humidity storage (Cantwell and Reid, 1993). Quality characteristics such as a fresh appearance, uniformity in leaf size, form, and color, characteristic aroma and flavor, and the absence of defects like decay or yellowing can be maintained through improved postharvest techniques (Cantwell and Reid, 1993). Coriander, as a leafy vegetable, undergoes rapid senescence at high temperatures post-harvest (Lipton, 1987; Paull, 1992).

While there are reports on the effect of hydrocooling on various leafy vegetables, including coriander, to reduce field heat, there is a lack of information on the synergistic effect of hydrocooled water and the impact of storage at low temperatures on the post-harvest quality and longevity of coriander leaves. Therefore, this study was designed to explore the impact of hydrocooling on the postharvest quality and shelf life of coriander leaves under different low-temperature storage conditions.

Materials and methods

The study took place at the Postharvest Laboratory within the Department of Horticulture at Patuakhali Science and Technology University. The experiment, featuring two factors, was organized using a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) and included five replications. Four hydro-cooling treatments (cool water at 5 ± 0.5 °C) were considered for factor A: T₁: Hydrocooling for 5 minutes (min), T₂: Hydrocooling for 10 min, T₃: Hydrocooling for 20 min, and T₄: Hydrocooling for 40 min; and two low-temperature storage treatments (at 4 ± 0.5 °C) were considered for factor B: S₁: Storage in a chiller and S₂: Storage in a refrigerator. The total number of treatment combinations was 4 (Factor A) × 2 (Factor B) × 5 (Replication) = 40. Locally cultivated leaves of the hybrid coriander variety were obtained from a nearby farmer's field as experimental material. The temperature of the surrounding environment and coriander leaves during harvesting from the field was 19.0 °C and 17.9 °C, respectively. The collected leaves were initially wrapped in newspaper and then encased in polythene before being

Hydrocooling and storage conditions on coriander leaf conveyed to the postharvest laboratory. Following that, the coriander leaves were diligently washed using running tap water to remove soil and other dust particles from their surfaces. Excess water from the leaves was removed by spreading them on a perforated tray at a room temperature of 19.5 °C with 83.0% relative humidity. A bundle of coriander leaves, weighing 50 g, was prepared by tying them together with a rubber band, and this served as an experimental unit.

Initially, the hydrocooling machine was filled with fresh tap water, and it was allowed to reach a water temperature of 5 (± 0.5) °C. Once the desired temperature was achieved, all 40 bundles of coriander leaf samples were immersed in the hydrocooled water to undergo the hydrocooling treatment. Subsequently, they were submerged in the hydro cooled water for the specified duration (5 minutes for 10 bundles, 10 minutes for 10 bundles, 20 minutes for 10 bundles, and 40 minutes for 10 bundles) to reduce the temperature of the bundle leaves to 5 (± 0.5) °C. After the hydrocooling treatment, the bundle sheet samples were placed in food boxes (20 cm × 15 cm × 6 cm) and wrapped with transparent food-grade polythene sheets. The boxes containing coriander leaves were then transferred to both a chiller and a normal refrigerator for low-temperature storage treatments at 4 ± 0.5 °C.

Observations on the shelf life of coriander leaves were recorded through visual assessments. The shelf life was determined from the initiation of storage until any signs of decay or spots appeared on the fresh leaves, which were examined daily at 10 AM. The quality of the leaves was visually scored throughout the storage period using an evaluation index (scores) ranging from 9 to 1, following the modified criteria established by Singh *et al.* (1972).

Table 1. Evaluation index on shelf life of coriander leaf by visual observation (Singh *et al.*, 1972)

Numerical rating	Descriptive rating	Visual observation
9	Excellent (maximum commercial value)	Field fresh, bright green appearance and free from defects
7	Good (commercial value)	Minor defects but not objectionable, green color is slightly bleached and dull, good retail sales appeal
5	Fair (limit of marketability)	Leaves showing slight yellowing and wilting, could be returned to acceptable condition with slight trimming
3	Poor (usable but unsalable)	Moderate yellowing, wilting and drying and other defects serious, would be eaten
1	Very poor (unusable)	Heavy yellowing, wilting and drying, other defects serious, would not be eaten

The pH was measured using a glass electrode pH meter (GLP 21, Crison, Barcelona, EEC). Titratable acidity (TA) and ascorbic acid (Vitamin C) were determined following the methods established by Rangana (1977) and Rangana (1979), respectively. The total anthocyanin content of the coriander leaf was determined according to the method described by Sims and Gamon (2002). The collected data on various parameters were statistically analyzed using Minitab Statistical software version 17 (Minitab Inc. State College, PA, USA); and the means were separated using Tukey at a 1% level of probability.

Results and discussion

Shelf life

Influence of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on the shelf life of coriander leaves

The shelf life of coriander leaves varied significantly ($p < 0.01$) among hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions (Figure 1a and Figure 1b). Treatment T₂, involving hydrocooling for 10 minutes, exhibited the longest shelf life (8.67 days), while the shortest shelf life (7.67 days) was observed in treatments T₁ and T₃. This suggests that coriander leaves can be stored for an additional day when treated with 10-minute hydrocooling duration (T₂) compared to treatments T₁ and T₃. The findings imply that the shelf life of coriander leaves tends to increase with the duration of hydrocooling treatment up to a certain point, after which it decreases due to prolonged chilling effects. Fredericci *et al.* (2019) reported an increase in the shelf life of spring onions when hydrocooled for 10 minutes at 5 °C. In contrast to our findings, a previous study by Franca *et al.* (2015) reported an extended shelf life in butter lettuce when hydrocooled at 4 °C for 5 minutes, followed by storage at 5 °C. In our investigation, the maximum shelf life (8.17 days) for coriander leaves was recorded in storage condition S₂ (refrigerator storage), while the minimum shelf life (7.83 days) was recorded in S₁ (chiller storage) at 4 ± 0.5 °C. The shorter shelf life in the chiller storage condition may be attributed to increased vapor generation, leading to more rapid leaf deterioration. Patel *et al.* (2015) observed an increased shelf life of tomatoes when hydrocooled at 8 °C and stored in refrigerated condition.

Figure 1. Effect of hydrocooling treatments (a) and storage conditions (b) on shelf life of coriander leaves. Here, T₁= hydrocooling for 5 minutes, T₂= hydrocooling for 10 minutes, T₃= hydrocooling for 20 minutes, T₄= hydrocooling for 40 minutes at 5 ± 0.5 °C; and S₁= storage at chiller, S₂= storage at refrigerator at 4 ± 0.5 °C. The vertical bars represent the standard error of the mean (n=5). In a column, values having a different letter (s) differ significantly at a 1% level of probability analyzed by Tukey.

Combined effect of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on the shelf life of coriander leaves

The combination of hydrocooling duration and storage condition had a significant impact ($p < 0.01$) on the shelf life of coriander leaves (Table 2 and Figure 2). The coriander leaves treated with hydrocooling for 10 minutes followed by storage in the refrigerator (T₂S₂) exhibited the longest shelf life (9.33 days), whereas the sample treated with 20 minutes of hydrocooling followed by storage in the refrigerator (T₃S₂) had the shortest shelf life (7.33 days) at 4 ± 0.5 °C.

Table 2. Combined effect of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on the shelf life of coriander leaves

Hydrocooling treatment × Storage condition	Shelf life
T ₁ S ₁	7.67 d
T ₁ S ₂	7.67 d
T ₂ S ₁	8.00 c
T ₂ S ₂	9.33 a
T ₃ S ₁	8.00 c
T ₃ S ₂	7.33 e
T ₄ S ₁	7.67 d
T ₄ S ₂	8.33 b
Level of significance	**
CV (%)	9.88

Here, T₁= hydrocooling for 5 minutes, T₂= hydrocooling for 10 minutes, T₃= hydrocooling for 20 minutes, T₄= hydrocooling for 40 minutes at 5 ± 0.5 °C; S₁= Storage at chiller, S₂= Storage at refrigerator at 4 ± 0.5 °C. ** = Significant at 1% level of probability. In a column, values having a different letter (s) differ significantly at 1% level of probability analyzed by Tukey.

Hydrocooling treatments

Figure 2. Hydrocooling treated samples: T₁ (5 min), T₂ (10 min), T₃ (20 min), and T₄ (40 min) in chiller and refrigerator in different days after storage (0, 7, 10 and 13).

pH

Influence of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on the pH content of coriander leaves

A significant difference ($p < 0.01$) in the pH of coriander leaves was evident across various hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions at intervals of 0, 7, and 10 days, as well as 10 and 13 days (Figure 3a and 3b). At 10 days, the highest pH (6.38) was observed for T₁ (hydrocooling for 5 minutes), which was statistically similar to T₂ and T₄, while the lowest pH (6.30) was recorded for T₃ (hydrocooling for 20 minutes). There was a slight increase in the pH of coriander leaves with

different hydrocooling treatments as the storage period progressed. Ferreira *et al.* (2006) reported that hydrocooling resulted in superior strawberry quality, including improvements in pH. The pH of coriander leaves gradually increased with different storage conditions as the storage duration advanced. On the 13th day of storage, a greater pH value (6.45) was noted in S₂ (refrigerator storage), while a lower pH (6.39) was registered in S₁ (chiller). The findings indicate an upward trend in the pH of coriander leaves during the later stages of storage, with variations based on the storage condition.

Figure 3. Effect of hydrocooling treatments (a) and storage conditions (b) on pH of coriander leaves

Here, T₁= hydrocooling for 5 minutes, T₂= hydrocooling for 10 minutes, T₃= hydrocooling for 20 minutes, T₄= hydrocooling for 40 minutes at 5 ± 0.5 °C. S₁= Storage at chiller, S₂= Storage at refrigerator at 4 ± 0.5 °C. The vertical bars represent the standard error of the mean (n=5). In a column, values having a different letter (s) differ significantly at 1% level of probability analyzed by Tukey.

Combined effect of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on the pH content of coriander leaves

There was a significant ($p < 0.01$) variation in the combined effects of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on the pH content of coriander leaves at 7, 10,

and 13 days after storage, whereas the combined was insignificant at the beginning (0 days) of the storage period (Table 3). At 13 days after storage, the highest pH (6.67) was recorded in T₁S₂, and the lowest pH (6.26) was observed in T₃S₂.

Table 3. Combined effect of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on pH of coriander leaves

Hydrocooling treatment × Storage condition	0 days	7 Days	10 Days	13 Days
T ₁ S ₁	6.25	6.34 a	6.30 cd	6.42 cd
T ₁ S ₂	6.25	6.34 a	6.45 a	6.67 a
T ₂ S ₁	6.02	6.07 b	6.25 d	6.37 d
T ₂ S ₂	6.02	6.06 b	6.50 a	6.54 b
T ₃ S ₁	6.00	6.08 b	6.31 c	6.40 d
T ₃ S ₂	6.00	6.08 b	6.30 cd	6.26 e
T ₄ S ₁	6.01	6.06 b	6.35 bc	6.38 d
T ₄ S ₂	6.01	6.06 b	6.38 b	6.47 c
Level of significance	NS	**	**	**
CV (%)	0.24	0.34	0.34	0.27

Here, T₁= hydrocooling for 5 minutes, T₂= hydrocooling for 10 minutes, T₃= hydrocooling for 20 minutes, T₄= hydrocooling for 40 minutes at 5 ± 0.5 °C; S₁= Storage at chiller, S₂= Storage at refrigerator at 4 ± 0.5 °C. ** = Significant at 1% level of probability. NS= non-significant. In a column, values having a different letter (s) differ significantly at 1% level of probability analyzed by Tukey.

Titrateable acidity

Influence of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on the titrateable acidity of coriander leaves

There was a significant ($p < 0.01$) variation among hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions at 0, 7, and 10 days after storage concerning the titrateable acidity of coriander leaves; however, at 13 days after storage, no significant difference was found (Figure 4a and 4b). On the 10th day following storage, T₄ exhibited the highest titrateable acidity at 0.23%, while T₁ showed the lowest titrateable acidity at 0.19%, with statistically similar to T₂ and T₃. Chepngeno *et al.* (2016) reported

that hydrocooling contributed to a deceleration in the reduction of titrateable acidity in vegetables. The titrateable acidity of coriander leaves gradually decreased with the progression of the storage period with different hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions. On the other hand, at 10 days after storage, the higher titrateable acidity (0.21%) of coriander leaves was observed when stored in the refrigerator (S₂), and the lower titrateable acidity (0.19%) was recorded in the chiller (S₁). Barbara *et al.* (2000) observed a lesser decrease (8%) in titrateable acidity when oranges were stored in the refrigerator, aligning with our own findings.

Figure 4. Effect of hydrocooling treatments (a) and storage conditions (b) on titratable acidity of coriander leaves

Here, T₁= hydrocooling for 5 minutes, T₂= hydrocooling for 10 minutes, T₃= hydrocooling for 20 minutes, T₄= hydrocooling for 40 minutes at 5 ± 0.5 °C. S₁= Storage at chiller, S₂= Storage at refrigerator at 4 ± 0.5 °C. The vertical bars represent the standard error of the mean (n=5). In a column, values having a different letter (s) differ significantly at 1% level of probability analyzed by Tukey.

Combined effect of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on the titratable acidity of coriander leaves

Significant differences ($p < 0.01$) were observed in the combined effects between hydrocooling treatment and

storage conditions at 0, 7, and 10 days post-storage, with no significant influence noted at 13 days post-storage (Table 4). On the 10th day of storage, T₄S₂ exhibited the highest titratable acidity at 0.26%, while all other treatments displayed the lowest titratable acidity at 0.19%.

Table 4. Combined effect of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on titratable acidity of coriander leaves

Hydrocooling treatment × Storage condition	0 Days	7 Days	10 Days	13 Days
T ₁ S ₁	0.38 a	0.26 a	0.19 b	0.19
T ₁ S ₂	0.26 c	0.26 a	0.19 b	0.19
T ₂ S ₁	0.32 b	0.19 b	0.19 b	0.19
T ₂ S ₂	0.13 d	0.19 b	0.19 b	0.19
T ₃ S ₁	0.32 b	0.19 b	0.19 b	0.19
T ₃ S ₂	0.13 d	0.26 a	0.19 b	0.19
T ₄ S ₁	0.38 a	0.19 b	0.19 b	0.19
T ₄ S ₂	0.13 d	0.19 b	0.26 a	0.19
Level of significance	**	**	**	NS
CV (%)	0.74	0.53	0.59	0.74

Here, T₁= hydrocooling for 5 minutes, T₂= hydrocooling for 10 minutes, T₃= hydrocooling for 20 minutes, T₄= hydrocooling for 40 minutes at 5 ± 0.5 °C; S₁= Storage at chiller, S₂= Storage at refrigerator at 4 ± 0.5 °C. ** = Significant at 1% level of probability. NS= non-significant. In a column, values having a different letter (s) differ significantly at 1% level of probability analyzed by Tukey.

Ascorbic acid content

Influence of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on the ascorbic acid content of coriander leaves

It is evident from Figure 4 that there was a significant ($p < 0.01$) variation among different hydrocooling treatments at 0, 7, and 10 days after storage, and storage conditions showed significant differences at 10 days after storage in terms of the ascorbic acid content of coriander leaves. The ascorbic acid content of coriander leaves was non-significant at 10 days among different treatments, and in the case of storage conditions, it was also non-significant at 0, 7, and 13 days (Figure 5a and 5b). The ascorbic acid content in coriander leaves diminished progressively as the storage period advanced, considering various hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions. At 10 days, the highest ascorbic acid content (5.0%) was recorded in hydrocooling treatment T₁

(hydrocooled for 5 minutes), while the lowest (3.75%) was observed in T₂ (hydrocooled for 10 minutes). The findings revealed that coriander leaves exhibited 33.33% higher ascorbic acidity when hydrocooled for 5 minutes (T₁) compared to hydrocooling for 10 minutes (T₂). Rivera *et al.* (2006) noted a rise in ascorbic acid levels in leaf lettuce for a period of up to 7 days as a result of hydrocooling. In terms of storage conditions, higher ascorbic acid content (3.75%) was observed when coriander leaves were stored in the refrigerator (S₂), and the lower ascorbic acid content (2.81%) was recorded when coriander leaves were stored in the chiller (S₁). It means that storage of coriander leaves in the refrigerator (S₂) can conserve 33.45% higher ascorbic acid than that of the chiller (S₁). Yadav & Sehgal (1997) reported a reduced loss of ascorbic acid in leafy vegetables when stored in a refrigerator at 5 °C.

Figure 5. Effect of hydrocooling treatments (a) and storage conditions (b) on ascorbic acid content of coriander leaves. Here, T₁= hydrocooling for 5 minutes, T₂= hydrocooling for 10 minutes, T₃= hydrocooling for 20 minutes, T₄= hydrocooling for 40 minutes at 5 ± 0.5 °C. S₁= Storage at chiller, S₂= Storage at refrigerator at 4 ± 0.5 °C. The vertical bars represent the standard error of the mean (n=5). In a column, values having a different letter (s) differ significantly at 1% level of probability analyzed by Tukey.

Combined effect of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on the ascorbic acid content of coriander leaves

The combined effect showed significant ($p < 0.01$) differences at 0, 7, and 10 days in respect to the ascorbic

acid content of coriander leaves, whereas a non-significant difference was observed at 13 days after storage (Table 4). At 10 days after storage, the highest ascorbic acid content of coriander leaves (5.01%) was recorded from T₁S₂, whereas the lowest (2.50%) was recorded in T₂S₁, T₃S₁, T₄S₁, and T₄S₂.

Table 5. Combined effect of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on ascorbic acid content of coriander leaves

Hydrocooling treatment x Storage Condition	0 Days	7 Days	10 Days	13 Days
T ₁ S ₁	5.00 a	5.01 a	3.75 b	2.50
T ₁ S ₂	5.00 a	5.00 a	5.01 a	2.50
T ₂ S ₁	3.75 b	3.75 b	2.50 c	2.50
T ₂ S ₂	3.75 b	3.75 b	3.75 b	2.51
T ₃ S ₁	3.76 b	3.76 b	2.50 c	2.50
T ₃ S ₂	3.76 b	3.74 b	3.75 b	2.50
T ₄ S ₁	3.76 b	3.75 b	2.50 c	2.50
T ₄ S ₂	3.76 b	3.75 b	2.50 c	2.49
Level of significance	**	**	**	NS
CV (%)	0.68	1.01	0.46	0.63

Here, T₁= hydrocooling for 5 minutes, T₂= hydrocooling for 10 minutes, T₃= hydrocooling for 20 minutes, T₄= hydrocooling for 40 minutes at 5 ± 0.5 °C; S₁= Storage at chiller, S₂= Storage at refrigerator at 4 ± 0.5 °C. ** = Significant at 1% level of probability. NS= non-significant. In a column, values having a different letter (s) differ significantly at 1% level of probability analyzed by Tukey.

Anthocyanin content

Influence of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on the anthocyanin content of coriander leaves

A significant ($p < 0.01$) difference in anthocyanin content of coriander leaves was observed after 7 days of treatments and storage. For both hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions, anthocyanin content remained insignificant at 0, 10, and 13 days (Figure 6a and 6b). After 7 days of storage, treatment T₁ showed the highest anthocyanin content (0.33 µg/g), while the lowest anthocyanin content (0.19 µg/g) was observed in treatment T₄. This indicates that coriander leaves

hydrocooled for 10 minutes (T₁) exhibited 73.68% more anthocyanin content than those hydrocooled for 40 minutes (T₄). Sena *et al.* (2019) documented a higher preservation of anthocyanins in cashew apples when subjected to hydrocooling. Additionally, after 7 days of storage, significantly higher anthocyanin content (0.28 µg/g) was recorded in S₂, while a lower content (0.25 µg/g) was observed in S₁. The results suggest that coriander leaves stored in the refrigerator (S₂) exhibited a 12% higher anthocyanin content compared to those stored in the chiller (S₁). Crifo *et al.* (2012) noted an increase in anthocyanin content in blood oranges with short-term cold storage at 4 °C.

Figure 6. Effect of hydrocooling treatments (a) and storage conditions (b) on anthocyanin content of coriander leaves. Here, T₁= hydrocooling for 5 minutes, T₂= hydrocooling for 10 minutes, T₃= hydrocooling for 20 minutes, T₄= hydrocooling for 40 minutes at 5 ± 0.5 °C. S₁= Storage at chiller, S₂= Storage at refrigerator at 4 ± 0.5 °C. The vertical bars represent the standard error of the mean (n=5). In a column, values having a different letter (s) differ significantly at 1% level of probability analyzed by Tukey.

Combined effect of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on the anthocyanin content of coriander leaves

The combined effect of different hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions showed a significant ($p < 0.01$) variation in anthocyanin content of coriander leaves at 7 and 10 days after storage, whereas a non-

significant difference was observed at 0 and 13 days (Table 5). At 10 days after storage, higher anthocyanin content (0.26 µg/g) was recorded in T₂S₁ and T₂S₂, while lower anthocyanin content (0.19 µg/g) was observed in T₄S₂.

Table 6. Combined effect of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions on anthocyanin content of coriander leaves

Hydrocooling treatment x Storage Condition	0 Days	7 Days	10 Days	13 Days
T ₁ S ₁	0.02	0.27 b	0.25 ab	0.26
T ₁ S ₂	0.02	0.39 a	0.23 ab	0.25
T ₂ S ₁	0.02	0.26 b	0.26 a	0.25
T ₂ S ₂	0.02	0.26 b	0.26 a	0.26
T ₃ S ₁	0.02	0.26 b	0.25 ab	0.26
T ₃ S ₂	0.02	0.26 b	0.26 ab	0.26
T ₄ S ₁	0.02	0.19 c	0.22 ab	0.26
T ₄ S ₂	0.02	0.19 c	0.19 b	0.26
Level of significance	NS	**	**	NS
CV (%)	9.75	0.70	0.75	0.62

Here, T₁= hydrocooling for 5 minutes, T₂= hydrocooling for 10 minutes, T₃= hydrocooling for 20 minutes, T₄= hydrocooling for 40 minutes at 5 ± 0.5 °C; S₁= Storage at chiller, S₂= Storage at refrigerator at 4 ± 0.5 °C. ** = Significant at 1% level of probability. NS= non-significant. In a column, values having a different letter (s) differ significantly at 1% level of probability analyzed by Tukey.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the study underscores the importance of hydrocooling treatments and storage conditions in influencing the shelf life and quality attributes of coriander leaves. Optimal hydrocooling for 10 minutes significantly extended shelf life, emphasizing the need for precise post-harvest handling. Refrigerator storage outperformed the chiller, highlighting the critical role of storage conditions. The investigation revealed fluctuations in pH, titratable acidity, ascorbic acid, and anthocyanin content, providing a comprehensive understanding of post-harvest dynamics. The longest shelf life was achieved through optimal hydrocooling for 10 minutes, followed by storage in the refrigerator, indicating a significant combined effect. However, fluctuations were observed in pH, titratable acidity, ascorbic acid, and anthocyanin content. These findings offer practical insights for enhancing the freshness and nutritional value of coriander leaves, benefiting both producers and consumers in the agricultural chain.

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